

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Thermal Conductivity Measurements of Hair and The Influence of Thermal Protectants

The following Application Highlight addresses the thermal conductivity measurement of human hair using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method.

To achieve a desired style, hair can be subjected to various thermal, mechanical and chemical treatments. These can include straightening or curling via thermal tools, detangling via brushing or changing colors using various chemical dyes. While fashionable, these treatments can have damaging effects on the hair structure, primarily through attack of the protective outer most layer (cuticle). While various products can be used to repair and/or prevent hair damage, ultimately these treatments can cause harm, especially if frequently applied. From a thermal perspective, heat damage occurs through the conversion of α -keratin (fibrous protein that makes up >95% of the hair follicle) to β -keratin (structurally weaker form) resulting in a loss of elasticity and making it more easily prone to subsequent damage. To better understand the negative influence heat treatments can have on hair and how to combat them, thermal properties such as thermal conductivity and heat capacity are often highlighted as key attributes of interest.

Figure 1. Left) Depiction of damaged vs healthy hair, Right) Different types of hair damage.

Thermal conductivity is important as it relates to the ability of the hair to handle the heat generated from various thermal applications. Measuring thermal conductivity of hair can be challenging due to the small size of the individual fibers (in the range of 70 μm diameter). Thermal conductivity instruments can vary with regards to sample size requirements, however in all cases, samples of this size are well below what is required for commercially available instrumentation. While direct measurements of individual strands are not currently possible, bundling of hair into a macro structure (think ponytail) can be used to better understand the effective thermal behaviour. Variables of the hair bundle such as hair diameter, density, assembly pattern, etc. can influence results, similar to how textiles and fabrics have been shown to behave. The following is an example dataset collected on a human hair extension piece using C-Therm's MTPS method. Results are the average of 5 consecutive measurements,

repeated in triplicate. The hair was bundled together and tested in the though-thickness direction under a 500gF compressive load under ambient conditions.

Figure 2. Thermal conductivity results of hair bundle (n=5).

An interesting application for thermal conductivity of hair is how various products can alter thermal heat dissipation performance. To protect hair, many will employ the use of a “thermal protectant” in the form of shampoo, conditioner, pre-treatment spray, leave in conditioner, etc. To see how these types of products influence thermal conductivity a leave in conditioner noted to have thermal protection properties was applied to the hair bundle and subsequently re-tested in a similar manner as previously highlighted. To ensure any differences were related to the product’s protective properties and not simply due to partial saturation of the sample, the sprayed bundle was dried for 30 mins under a continuous flow of cool air. The sample was then left to further dry overnight and retested ~12 hours later. Results from this can be found in the figure below.

Figure 3. Thermal conductivity results of hair bundle before and after application of a thermal protectant.

Results from the above indicate a notable increase in thermal conductivity (~36%) compared to the untreated sample. Measurements taken after 12 hours showed a slight decrease in thermal

conductivity, however still significantly higher than the untreated baseline. These results indicate that the application of this product can provide an improvement on heat dissipation performance, contributing to a decrease in potential damage from thermal treatments.

While values of thermal conductivity of hair fibers have been reported through calculated methods to be 0.25W/mK (using heat capacity data), understanding the effective properties of a bulk grouping of hair through direct measurements can be of great value. The interstitial air formed in the bundles introduces a much lower effective thermal conductivity (as highlighted in the data above). Tools such as a curling wand work by taking bundled strands of hair and pressing them together around a heat source and as such the effective conductivity of a hair bundle may provide more representative data for product development and optimization, rather than that of a single hair fiber. The ability to test hair that has undergone various treatments or after product applications can provide valuable insight into how the thermal properties have been influenced and how to better develop these tools and products to repair/reduce any negative changes from occurring in the future.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit
www.TridentThermalConductivity.com